

Article

Effects of Parental Engagement and Learner Conduct on Educational Outcomes

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Abstract: This study investigated the relationship between parental presence and the behavior of Grade 3 learners using a descriptive-correlational design. Data were collected from 24 parents and one teacher through adapted survey questionnaires. Descriptive statistics were used to profile the learners, while Pearson's correlation coefficient was applied to examine the relationship between parental involvement and learner behavior. The results revealed a significant moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.616$, $p = 0.001$), indicating that increased parental presence is associated with more positive behavioral outcomes among learners. Specifically, higher parental involvement correlated with better cooperation, attentiveness, and respect for teachers and peers. However, the moderate strength of the relationship suggests that other factors, such as peer influence and school environment, also play a role in shaping behavior. These findings underscore the importance of school-family partnerships in supporting both academic and behavioral development in learners, while also calling for a more holistic approach to student support.

Keywords: Parental presence, learner behavior, parental involvement, school engagement, educational support

Introduction

Academic performance is a crucial indicator of student success, reflecting cognitive, social, and emotional competencies that are foundational for future achievements (Jones & White, 2021). In educational contexts, academic performance not only provides insight into student progress but also informs instructional practices and educational policies (Baker & Green, 2020). High academic performance is consistently linked to better career prospects and enhanced life satisfaction (Lerner et al., 2021). Beyond the classroom, academic success fosters critical thinking, problem-solving, and engagement in society (Zhao et al., 2023). Moreover, academic

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performance shapes students' long-term aspirations and quality of life (Green et al., 2022). Thus, it is essential to examine factors that influence academic performance, both facilitating and impeding it, to enhance student outcomes (Wang & Eccles, 2020).

External factors, such as family background, social environment, and school climate, significantly influence academic outcomes (Nguyen et al., 2022). Parental involvement and student behavior are among the most critical determinants (Olivares & García, 2021). Research suggests that active parental involvement fosters positive learning attitudes, increases motivation, and enhances engagement (Kim & Lee, 2023). Moreover, students' behaviors, including their ability to concentrate, follow instructions, and collaborate with peers, are directly linked to academic achievement (Kenny & Stevens, 2020). Positive behaviors like self-regulation and cooperation are often associated with higher academic success, while disruptive behaviors can negatively affect academic outcomes (Clark et al., 2022). Understanding how these internal and external factors intersect is crucial for developing effective educational strategies (Thompson & Green, 2021).

Parental presence, defined as active involvement in home-based and school-based educational activities, has been shown to positively influence students' academic performance (Wilder, 2020). Studies highlight that parental engagement in activities such as attending school meetings, assisting with homework, and participating in school events correlates positively with students' academic outcomes (Fan & Chen, 2021). Parental involvement also provides emotional and academic support, creating a stable home environment conducive to learning (Garcia & Fields, 2022). Continuous engagement by parents enhances not only cognitive development but also emotional and behavioral growth, which are critical for academic success (Miller & Baker, 2022). This involvement is particularly important in early childhood education, where parental support plays a significant role in fostering positive attitudes toward learning and building a strong foundation for future success (Phillips et al., 2022).

Student behavior also plays a pivotal role in academic success. Behaviors such as attentiveness, participation, and collaboration in the classroom are strongly linked to improved academic performance (Wright & Taylor, 2022). Research indicates that students who demonstrate perseverance, self-control, and cooperation tend to perform better academically than their peers who exhibit disruptive behaviors (Hattie et al., 2020). Studies further suggest that parental presence can help mitigate negative behaviors, thereby creating a more supportive and focused learning environment (Jones & Biddle, 2021). Therefore, exploring the relationship between parental involvement and student behavior is essential for understanding the broader impact on academic achievement (González et al., 2023).

In early childhood education, parental involvement and student behavior are key factors that significantly influence long-term academic

outcomes (Crosnoe & Leventhal, 2023). Studies have shown that parental engagement during the early years promotes cognitive, social, and emotional development, which are essential for academic success (Bronson et al., 2020). Moreover, early education provides a foundation for positive learning behaviors, including curiosity, persistence, and cooperation (Walker & Greene, 2023). Given the importance of these formative years, it is crucial to understand the relationship between parental involvement, behavior, and academic performance (Fisher & Jenkins, 2021). This research aims to contribute to this growing body of literature by providing insights into how these factors intersect, particularly in the context of early childhood education.

Although numerous studies have established the link between parental involvement and academic success, limited research explores how parental presence specifically influences student behavior in early childhood settings. This study seeks to address this gap by examining the influence of parental presence on the behavior of Grade 3 learners. It focuses on several research questions: What are the learners' profiles in terms of age, gender, parents' educational attainment, number of siblings, and family income? To what extent do parents manifest their presence in school activities? What is the perceived level of learners' behavior, as reported by teachers? By addressing these questions, this study aims to clarify how parental involvement and student behavior intersect to influence academic performance (Kim et al., 2021).

The study will provide valuable contributions to the literature on parental involvement and its effects on student behavior and academic performance. Through an in-depth analysis of Grade 3 learners, it will examine how parental engagement shapes both behavioral and academic outcomes. The findings are expected to offer practical recommendations for educators, policymakers, and parents, promoting strategies to support behavioral and academic development. Furthermore, the research will lay the groundwork for fostering stronger school-family partnerships, which are critical for improving educational outcomes in early childhood education learner behavior, this study aims to address significant gaps in the current literature and contribute meaningful insights to the field.

Methodology

This study utilized a descriptive-correlational design to explore the impact of parental presence on the behavior of Grade 3 learners at Kangwayan Elementary School. This design was selected because it allowed for a comprehensive examination of the learners' demographic characteristics, such as age, gender, parents' highest educational attainment, number of siblings, and family income, while also investigating the relationship between these factors and learner behavior. Data were collected from 25 respondents, including 24 parents and one teacher, using two adapted survey questionnaires. These questionnaires, derived from validated instruments to ensure

reliability and validity, captured demographic information from parents and assessed parental involvement in school activities using a 4-point Likert scale. The teacher's questionnaire evaluated learner behavior, focusing on attentiveness, respect for authority, and cooperation, also using a 4-point Likert scale.

Both descriptive and inferential statistical methods were employed to analyze the data. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were used to summarize respondent profiles. Pearson's correlation coefficient was applied to assess the strength and direction of the relationship between parental presence and learner behavior, providing insights into whether increased parental involvement was linked to more favorable behavioral outcomes. This correlational analysis was essential in testing the hypothesis that parental presence positively influences learner behavior. The data collection process followed a structured, three-stage approach preliminary stage, data collection, and post-collection analysis to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the findings. Overall, this methodology provided a robust framework for understanding how parental presence affects student behavior and offered valuable recommendations for enhancing parental involvement in educational settings.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Age and Gender

Age (in years)	Female		Male		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
9	2	8.33	2	8.33	4	16.67
8	7	29.17	11	45.83	18	75.00
7	0	0.00	2	8.33	2	8.33
Total	9	37.50	15	62.50	24	100.00

Table 1 presents the distribution of Grade 3 learners at Kangwayan Elementary School by age and gender. The data shows that the majority of learners (75%) are 8 years old, with 29.17% of these being female and 45.83% being male. The next largest age group is 9-year-olds, making up 16.67% of the total population, with an equal distribution of 8.33% for both females and males. Lastly, 8.33% of the learners are 7 years old, all of whom are male. In total, the population consists of 37.50% females and 62.50% males, indicating a higher number of male learners in this Grade 3 cohort. The predominance of 8-year-olds suggests that most learners fall within the typical age range for Grade 3, with a slight male dominance in the population.

Table 2 shows the highest educational attainment of the parents of Grade 3 learners at Kangwayan Elementary School, with separate data for mothers and fathers. Among the mothers, the largest group (37.50%) are high school graduates, followed by 16.67% who are college

graduates and another 16.67% who completed some high school education. A smaller proportion of mothers (12.50%) are elementary graduates, while 8.33% attended but did not finish elementary school, and 8.33% completed some college education.

Table 2. Parents' Highest Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Mother		Father	
	f	%	f	%
College Graduate	4	16.67	1	4.17
College Level	2	8.33	3	12.50
High School Graduate	9	37.50	7	29.17
High School Level	4	16.67	5	20.83
Elementary Graduate	3	12.50	2	8.33
Elementary Level	2	8.33	6	25.00
Total	24	100.00	24	100.00

For the fathers, the highest percentage (29.17%) are high school graduates, followed by 25.00% who completed elementary-level education. A smaller portion of fathers (20.83%) completed some high school education, and 12.50% have some college experience. Only 8.33% of fathers are elementary graduates, and 4.17% are college graduates. Overall, the data indicates that the majority of parents have a high school education, with fewer completing higher education. Fathers are more likely to have lower educational attainment (elementary level), while mothers show slightly higher rates of college graduation.

Table 3. Number of Siblings of the Learners

Number of Siblings	f	%
5 and up	4	16.67
3-4	15	62.50
1-2	5	20.83
Total	24	100.00

Table 3 presents the distribution of Grade 3 learners at Kangwayan Elementary School based on the number of siblings they have. The majority of learners (62.50%) come from families with 3-4 siblings, indicating that most learners belong to moderately sized families. Additionally, 20.83% of the learners have 1-2 siblings, while a smaller portion (16.67%) come from larger families with five or more siblings. These figures suggest that most learners come from families with multiple siblings, which may influence household dynamics and parental involvement in their education.

Table 4 presents the combined family monthly income of Grade 3 learners' households at Kangwayan Elementary School. The vast majority of the learners' families (87.50%) have a monthly income of

₱10,000 or below, indicating that most learners come from low-income households. A smaller portion (8.33%) of families have a monthly income between ₱10,001 and ₱15,000, while only 4.17% of families earn between ₱25,001 and ₱30,000.

Table 4. Combined Family Monthly Income

Monthly Income (in pesos)	f	%
25,001-30,000	1	4.17
20,001-25,000	0	0.00
15,001-20,000	0	0.00
10,001-15,000	2	8.33
10,000 and below	21	87.50
Total	24	100.00

Notably, no families fall within the ₱15,001 to ₱25,000 income brackets. This data suggests that the majority of learners come from economically disadvantaged backgrounds, which may have implications for access to educational resources and parental involvement in school activities.

Table 5. Extent to which the Respondents Manifest their Presence in the School Activities

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	I assist my child in their assignments, quizzes and recitations.	3.38	Highly Manifested
2	I attend in my child's extra-curricular activities/sports, singing competitions and etc.	3.08	Manifested
3	I let my child explore their learning process on their own.	3.38	Highly Manifested
4	I encourage my child to be more independent.	3.38	Highly Manifested
5	I attend to school meetings regularly.	3.21	Manifested
6	I frequently explain difficult ideas to my child when he doesn't understand.	3.33	Highly Manifested
7	I regularly visit my child's school.	2.71	Manifested
8	If my child misbehaved at school, I would know about it soon afterward.	3.38	Highly Manifested
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.23	Manifested

Table 5 summarizes the extent to which parents manifest their presence in school activities, based on several indicators measured using a 4-point Likert scale. The aggregate weighted mean of 3.23 indicates that, overall, parental presence in their child's educational activities is "Manifested." Specifically, parents "Highly Manifested" their involvement in assisting with assignments, quizzes, and recitations (WM = 3.38), encouraging independence (WM = 3.38), and knowing about their child's misbehavior at school (WM = 3.38). Parents also "Highly Manifested" explaining difficult concepts to their children (WM = 3.33). In other areas, such as attending extracurricular activities (WM = 3.08) and school meetings (WM = 3.21), parental presence was rated as "Manifested." The lowest rating was for regular school visits (WM = 2.71), which, although still manifested, was comparatively less frequent. These findings suggest that while parents are generally involved in their child's education, their involvement is more focused

on supporting learning at home and fostering independence, with less emphasis on physically attending school activities.

Table 6. Level of the Behavior of the Learners

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	Follows directions easily.	3.25	Excellent
2	Has a positive attitude (e.g usually optimistic and confident in handling academic obligations)	3.21	Satisfactory
3	Turns in homework and projects.	3.33	Excellent
4	Respectful of their teachers, parents and other older persons.	3.46	Excellent
5	Cooperates with others effortlessly. (e.g, classroom group activities)	3.25	Excellent
6	Easily gets along with other students.	3.08	Satisfactory
7	Brings materials for school activities.	3.25	Excellent
8	Asks for help from the teacher for clarifications.	3.13	Satisfactory
9	Has a neat workspace.	3.08	Satisfactory
10	Has a neat appearance.	3.21	Satisfactory
11	Listens attentively to the teacher in class and outside of class.	3.33	Excellent
12	Displays interest towards the lessons.	3.21	Satisfactory
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.23	Satisfactory

Table 6 presents the level of behavior of Grade 3 learners at Kangwayan Elementary School, as assessed using a 4-point Likert scale across various behavioral indicators. The aggregate weighted mean of 3.23 indicates that, overall, the learners' behavior is rated as "Satisfactory." Several indicators were rated as "Excellent," including "Respectful of their teachers, parents, and other older persons" (WM = 3.46), "Turns in homework and projects" (WM = 3.33), "Follows directions easily" (WM = 3.25), "Cooperates with others" (WM = 3.25), "Brings materials for school activities" (WM = 3.25), and "Listens attentively to the teacher" (WM = 3.33). Other areas, such as having a "Positive attitude" (WM = 3.21), "Easily gets along with other students" (WM = 3.08), "Asks for help from the teacher" (WM = 3.13), "Has a neat workspace" (WM = 3.08), and "Displays interest towards lessons" (WM = 3.21), were rated as "Satisfactory." Overall, while learners demonstrate excellent behavior in many key areas, certain behaviors, particularly those related to neatness, social interactions, and engagement in class, were found to be satisfactory, suggesting areas for potential improvement.

Table 7. Test of significant relationship between Parental Presence and Learners' Behavior

Variables	r-value	Strength of Correlation	p - value	Decision	Result
Parental Presence and Learners' Behavior	0.616*	Moderate Positive	0.001	Reject Ho	Significant

*significant at $p < 0.05$ (two-tailed)

Table 7 presents the test of the significant relationship between parental presence and learners' behavior. The Pearson correlation coefficient (r -value) of 0.616 indicates a moderate positive correlation between the two variables. With a p -value of 0.001, which is less than the significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected. This result demonstrates that there is a statistically significant relationship between parental presence and learners' behavior. Specifically, the findings suggest that increased parental involvement is associated with more positive behavioral outcomes among the Grade 3 learners. This moderate positive correlation implies that as parental presence in educational activities increases, the behavior of learners improves accordingly.

Discussion

The findings of this study reveal a significant moderate positive relationship between parental presence and learners' behavior, as evidenced by the Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = 0.616$, $p = 0.001$). This suggests that as parental involvement in school activities increases, learners exhibit more positive behaviors. This outcome is consistent with existing literature emphasizing the importance of parental engagement in shaping student behavior. For example, Wang and Eccles (2020) demonstrated that active parental participation in academic and extracurricular activities enhances students' self-regulation, cooperation, and respect for authority, leading to improved behavioral outcomes. Moreover, Kim et al. (2021) highlight that parental involvement not only supports cognitive development but also nurtures the social and emotional competencies that are essential for maintaining positive behavior in school settings. These findings also align with Bronson et al. (2020), who argue that parental presence provides a foundation for positive behavior by creating a supportive environment that encourages students to follow instructions, respect their peers and teachers, and actively engage in school tasks. However, while the correlation in this study is significant, it is moderate, suggesting that other factors beyond parental presence, such as peer interactions, teacher-student relationships, and individual learner characteristics, may also play a substantial role in shaping behavior. Crosnoe and Leventhal (2023) emphasize that a comprehensive approach to improving student behavior should involve both school and home environments, focusing not only on parental involvement but also on broader social and contextual factors that influence student behavior. Therefore, while enhancing parental presence is crucial,

schools should also consider strategies that address these other influential elements to foster an optimal learning environment.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates a significant moderate positive relationship between parental presence and the behavior of Grade 3 learners. The findings suggest that increased parental involvement is associated with improved behavioral outcomes, particularly in areas such as respect for authority, cooperation, and attentiveness. However, the moderate strength of this correlation indicates that other factors, including peer relationships, teacher-student interactions, and individual learner characteristics, may also influence learner behavior. These results highlight the importance of fostering strong school-family partnerships to enhance students' behavioral development. While parental presence plays a crucial role, a holistic approach that integrates both home and school environments is essential for supporting positive behavioral and academic outcomes. Further research should explore these additional factors to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the influences on student behavior.

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